

A Massive Clustering Algorithm for Fast Radio Resource Allocation to Distributed Units in O-RAN Networks

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Abstract

The progression towards fifth and sixth generation cellular networks (5G and 6G) radically alters network architectures, moving from traditional configurations to more dynamic and flexible structures. A key aspect of this transition is the disaggregation and virtualization of base station functionality into central units (CUs), distributed units (DUs) and radio units (RUs). The O-RAN Alliance is at the forefront of this change, introducing key innovations for radio access networks (RAN) in line with the vision of 3GPP. This paper introduces a new massive clustering algorithm for fast radio resource allocation in O-RAN networks, focusing on fronthaul topology optimization using advanced graph learning techniques on a very large driving test dataset. Specifically, we leverage the Leiden Algorithm to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of RU/CU clustering, thereby improving optimization and resource management within the RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC). Our results demonstrate the efficiency in allocating virtualized DU/CU capacities, highlighting the potential of integrating graph learning into the O-RAN framework to meet the needs of next-generation cellular networks.

Artificial Intelligence, Graph Learning, Clustering, Virtualization, Handovers, Open-RAN

1 Introduction

The evolution to fifth and sixth-generation mobile networks (5G and 6G) is revolutionising network architectures, moving from traditional, static configurations to more dynamic and adaptive structures. This transformation presents significant challenges, including effectively serving many users, meeting stringent delay and capacity requirements, and optimising network costs. Proposed by the O-RAN Alliance, the Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) reference architecture [1] offers a promising solution for next-generation RAN infrastructures [2] [3]. It introduces significant innovations that align with the 3GPP concept of virtualizing base station functionalities on open and interoperable devices. The architecture defined by the O-RAN Alliance comprises three primary units interconnected via standard interfaces: i) the Radio Unit (RU), which manages filtering and frequency transposition; ii) the Distributed Unit (DU), which is responsible for digital modulation, signal processing and retransmission; and iii) the Central Unit (CU), which handles IP packet transport and signalling. The separation and virtualisation of gNodeB functionality enable the RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC) to provide a unified

Figure 1: O-RAN Architecture Overview

network perspective. By decoupling the hardware and software components of the gNodeB, the RIC can manage and orchestrate radio resources and control plane capabilities adaptively, thus meeting different user plane needs and specific use cases. As a result, each operator can implement customised control plane policies, thereby improving the flexibility and programmability of 5G and 6G networks. Furthermore, virtualization and implementation of DU and CU functionality as microservices within O-RAN offer substantial benefits, particularly in reducing network management costs and improving the efficiency and scalability of resource utilization in response to the variable demand [4]. By leveraging cloud infrastructure, operators can reduce dependence on expensive proprietary hardware, enabling more flexible and scalable network operations. Moreover, DUs and CUs functionality virtualization enables their strategic placement in edge locations, reducing latency and ensuring fast response times for services that require low latency, such as vehicular communications in high mobility scenarios. In particular, 5G NR handover procedures (5G Inter gNodeB handover and 5G intra RAN handover) can benefit significantly from the intelligent control of the decentralized and virtualized nature of gNodeB units [5]. The RIC can use advanced clustering and graph learning algorithms to handle DU and CU functions. This AI-assisted orchestration ensures fast and efficient handover management, maintaining seamless connectivity and consistent quality of service as users transition between network cells [6] [7]. AI algorithms dynamically optimize network parameters in real-time, allowing the network to quickly adapt to changing mobility conditions, thereby reducing latency and improving connection reliability. Furthermore, O-RAN’s modular and open structure facilitates seamless integration and continuous updating of AI models using accurate and real-time data from driving tests. This capability improves system responsiveness and resilience to highly variable radio scenarios characteristic of high-mobility environments.

Contribution. In this paper, we introduce a graph learning approach for the optimal clustering of Radio Units (RUs) to be associated with virtualized Distributed Units (DUs) and Centralized Units (CUs) for enhanced network resource management during handovers. A weighted graph model is developed by integrating radio measurement reports from User Equipments (UEs) with data related to all beams detected by these UEs at specific geographical locations. In other words, we may deduce a snapshot of the mobile traffic at these geographical positions, i.e. number of users¹ and resources available in the neighbourhood of that location. The weighted graph model is the input to the Leiden Community Detection algorithm, which efficiently clusters Radio Units (RUs). Using the Leiden learning approach, the RIC can systematically organise RUs to form clusters of neighbouring RUs connected to the same DU/CU, mainly promoting intra-DU handovers over inter-DU or inter-CU transitions. As a result, the

¹5G MIMO may allow to allocate a beam to each user.

proposed strategic graph-based clustering significantly reduces signalling traffic and associated latencies as US handovers between cells, thereby reducing operational inefficiencies during handovers and improving QoE. Utilizing automated clustering will have an even more significant impact in 6G, where the RAN will be fully virtualized.

Figure 2: 5G handover types

Paper structure Section II explains the integration of graph learning into RIC for optimal network resource management. It details the use of graph theory to model Minimization Driving Test (MDT) data to cluster RUs. Section III provides an in-depth technical analysis of the Leiden algorithm for graphs in a RAN-like architecture. Section IV presents the radio measurements, comparable to MDT data, used in the experiments and the results of applying the proposed clustering algorithm to assign DUs to UEs efficiently. Section V summarizes the findings and suggests areas for further research.

2 Graph modelling for RAN management

The integration of graph learning into the RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC) marks a significant advancement in optimising and managing resources in mobile access networks [8] [9] [10]. Graph learning involves analyzing data and processes embedded in a graph structure using advanced machine learning algorithms explicitly designed for graphs. These algorithms range from conventional machine learning (ML) techniques, which learn and assign properties and weights to nodes or edges, to complex clustering methods that organize nodes based on network optimization metrics. Additionally, graph learning includes advanced AI algorithms such as Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) that capture and leverage the complex relationships in data structured as a graph, effectively making predictions based on the patterns and interactions among the network nodes.

This paper uses graph theory and graph learning to model radio-quality MDT data to identify clusters of RUs that are candidates to constitute the same virtualized DU. This approach aims to facilitate intra-DU handovers and optimize QoS for mobile users. Furthermore, the implementation of a robust RU clustering strategy is critical for effectively and efficiently optimising the RU-DU-CU topology. In fact, flexibility, efficiency and scalability of the access network are inherently linked to the functional split between Distributed Units (DUs) and Central Units (CUs), as well as the implementation and allocation of DU, CU-CP and CU-UP functionalities within the gNodeB. This allocation must be responsive to traffic demand, user mobility patterns and service requirements. CUs and DUs can be virtualized in centralized and edge cloud environments to enhance QoS and latency. The correct sizing of the hardware implementing and virtualising these O-RAN components enables future access networks to adapt rapidly to

fluctuations in traffic and demands of new service types, thereby reducing costs and enhancing operational efficiency.

2.1 MDT

MDT measurements gather and report network performance data, including signal strength and UL/DL radio quality metrics (RSRP, RSRQ, RSSI, SINR), GPS position and QoS metrics (throughput, data loss, latency), in real time under actual usage conditions. MDT supports two measurement modes: Logged MDT and Immediate MDT and additional cases such as Accessibility measurements. Logged MDT involves data collection over time with subsequent upload to the network, while Immediate MDT entails real-time data collection and reporting. MDT measurements can be configured for UE logging independently of the network’s normal Radio Resource Management (RRM) configurations. However, the availability of these measurement results often depends on the UE’s RRM configuration. Consequently, MDT offers a more comprehensive and representative view of network conditions compared to the limited snapshot provided by traditional drive tests (DT), facilitating precise and user-friendly data collection and enhancing network optimization and performance.

2.2 Graph Model from MDT Data

The proposed graph model aims to construct an accurate data-driven topology for the midhaul network segment. This model is expected to enhance the implementation, testing, and execution of specific AI algorithms designed for efficient radio resource management. In this study, we leverage the devised graph model to efficiently allocate virtualized Distributed Units (DUs) and central units (CUs) within the mid-haul network. The initial step in defining the network graph involves preprocessing, cleaning and clustering the MDT data to identify RU cells from radio measurements and geospatial information uniquely. The next step defines the virtualized DU and CU nodes that control a cluster of RU nodes within a given region.

The identification of RU nodes is achieved by analyzing the large number of downlink (DL) radio measurements collected by UEs and reported to the RIC. MDT operations in idle mode (*logged MDT*) are optional for each UE. In contrast, connected mode MDT operations (*immediate MDT*) are mandatory for UEs, except those to tag measurement reports with detailed location information, which are optional.

Given a target area of the access network graph for the DU partitioning, MDT radio measurements (such as RSRQ, RSRP, RSSI or SNR, SSB Index) can be grouped based on PCI, NRARFCN, beam index, area code and initial timestamp t of measurement cycles.

This grouping generates a set of graph nodes that partially define the RUs within the area. Each measurement at a given geographical location is further characterized by the estimated distance to the RU. In the majority of cases, user equipments (UEs) that is receiving both PSS (primary synchronization signal) and SSS (secondary synchronization signal) at a specific geographical location will detect signals from the nearest RUs. Thus, in each measurement cycle, MDT data are associated with different tuples (NRARFCN, PCI, beam index). This suggests characterizing each node with a hash value based on NRARFCN, PCI and area code.

A group of nodes with the same hash value identifies a single RU and provides implicit information about the set of necessary DUs and CUs to control these RUs.

In the graph modelling of the RAN, RU nodes will be described by the following key parameters: the NRARFCN (*New Radio Absolute Radio Frequency Channel Number*) and the PCI (Physical Cell ID). Each 5G NR cell corresponds to a PCI, however this identifier can distinguish cells on the radio side in a limited geographical area. In fact, in 5G networks, there are only 1008 unique PCI values, determined by the formula:

$$PCI = 3 * SSS + PSS \tag{1}$$

where $SSS \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 335\}$ and $PSS \in \{0, 1, 2\}$. Therefore, operators must assign PCI values so that neighbouring RUs (or those managed by the same DU/CU) do not share the same PCI value. Incorrect PCI planning can negatively impact synchronization, demodulation and handover procedures, ultimately degrading network performance. Nevertheless, distant RUs can share the same PCI and NRARFCN without causing communication issues. Thus, area code is necessary to compute the hash value associated with each graph node to disambiguate nodes with the same PCI and NRARFCN but existing at distant geographical locations. This approach disambiguates nodes with MDT data that contain identical NRARFCN and PCI pairs but refer to geographically distant positions.

Once the construction of graph nodes is completed, the set of graph edges is defined by associating: an edge between two nodes, if there exists a measurement cycle at timestamp t_i that reports the beam coming from the two RUs. We also construct a weight of the edge connecting these two nodes considering their co-occurrences' frequency. This weight is highly dependent on the actual traffic in the area and on that of the neighboring areas.

Furthermore, the MDT data can include radio signal quality metrics of different beams emitted by one or more neighbouring 5G RUs and the UE throughputs observed on the RAN side during a time interval for a sufficient number of users. Consequently, the graph derived from *MDT data* can offer valuable insights into traffic demand, including the number of users connected to the network at a specific geolocation or the QoS degradation due to interference or to a limited coverage.

3 Graph-Based RU Clustering with the Leiden Algorithm

The MDT graph provides insights into the radio coverage status of RUs and aids in optimizing DU allocation by clustering RU nodes based on their interconnections. The Leiden algorithm is employed to identify well-defined and stable clusters, ensuring robust community detection and effective handling of complex graphs. This implementation generates more accurate RU clusters, facilitates efficient allocation of DU/CU functionalities and improves QoS, thereby enhancing the overall reliability and scalability of 5G communication systems [11] [12]. From a mathematical perspective, the Leiden algorithm starts from an input graph $G(V, E)$, which may have weights for nodes $V = \{v_i\}$ and edges $E = \{e_{ij}\}$. It aggregates community nodes intending to optimise a quality function, such as the *Modularity* or the *Constant Potts Model (CPM)*. The *modularity function* of a graph is defined as:

$$\mathcal{H} = \sum_{ij} \left(W_{ij} - \gamma \cdot \frac{(w_i + w_j)^2}{2W} \right) \delta(\sigma(i), \sigma(j)) \quad (2)$$

where w_i and W_{ij} are node and edge weights, $\sigma(i)$ and $\sigma(j)$ are the clusters to which the nodes v_i and v_j belong respectively, γ is the resolution parameter and W is given by $W = \sum_i w_i$. The Kronecker delta $\delta(\sigma(i), \sigma(j))$ is 1 if $\sigma(i) = \sigma(j)$ and 0 otherwise. When the node weight w_i represents the node's outdegree or indegree and link exists between v_i and v_j ($W_{ij} = 1$), the eq. (2) represents the standard definition. The *Constant Potts Model function* is defined [13] as:

$$\mathcal{H}_{CPM} = \sum_{i,j} (W_{ij} - \gamma) \delta(\sigma(i), \sigma(j)) \quad (3)$$

The modularity compares the density of edges within communities to the expected density between communities in a randomized network. This parameter indicates how effectively the graph nodes are divided into clusters with higher internal edge density than expected. In contrast, the CPM function evaluates the quality of a community partition based on the difference between the actual edge weights within communities and a constant parameter γ . This parameter γ introduces flexibility by allowing control over the granularity of the communities detected. By

adjusting γ , the Leiden algorithm with CPM function identifies communities at different scales. This feature helps to overcome the resolution limit problem inherent in the modularity function, which often fails to identify smaller communities in large graphs.

To construct possible RU partition from the MDT graph, a simple weighting scheme was applied to nodes, counting the number of measurements cycles that include beams from both RU nodes. Then, the Leiden algorithm finds RU communities through four key stages:

- Initially, the Leiden algorithm optimizes modularity locally, akin to the Louvain method. Nodes are moved to neighbouring communities if this improves the partition quality.
- After the initial optimization, the algorithm refines communities by subdividing them. It identifies strongly connected subsets within each community, ensuring internal cohesion and avoiding poorly connected communities.
- The refined communities are then aggregated, with each community treated as a single node in a new, smaller network. The number of inter-community edges from the original network determines the edge weights between these new nodes.
- The iterative cycle of local moving, refinement, and aggregation is repeatedly executed. Each iteration progressively enhances the community structure until no further improvements are feasible, culminating in a stable and high-quality partition.

The RUs partitioning is influenced by the resolution parameter. A resolution value of 0.0001 was selected to create clusters with numerous elements, ensuring to initially create few clusters to be further partitioned. Indeed, we put a bound on the number of possible RU allowed to belong to each cluster so that the partitioning will best allocate 1008 RUs under the same DU still optimizing the objective function. Each cluster corresponds to a Distributed Unit (DU). This method optimizes the allocation of all RUs to DUs by considering both the observed traffic in the served geographical area and the constraint on the maximum number of RUs per cluster.

4 Experimental results

In this section, we apply graph learning to the radio and throughput measurements dataset collected by Ugo Bordoni Foundation² on the Italian highway and urban network. The objective was to monitor coverage and quality of service (QoS) of three 5G Mobile Network Operators (MNOs), identified in the following by assigning generic labels MNO_A , MNO_B , and MNO_C .

The measurements in the FUB dataset were obtained using Rohde & Schwarz’s technological monitoring tools, which assess the radio signal quality and throughputs at various protocol levels (PHY, MAC, RLC, PDCP, SDAP, RRC) on the RAN interface in both downlink and uplink. These measurements are comparable with the MDT data collected from UEs moving on the considered urban roads and highway networks. The dataset consists of 9,939,465 measurement sections, each lasting 10ms.

The Leiden algorithm used for testing is implemented in *Python* and sourced from the *leidenalg* library. This standalone implementation does not utilize parallelization across multiple cores. The tests were conducted in the following environment:

- Intel® Core™ i7-9750H CPU @ 2.60GHz \times 12, 32GB RAM; 16GiB SODIMM DDR4 2667MHz \times 2; 1TB SSD, KXG60ZNV1T02 KIOXIA; NVIDIA Corporation GP107GLM [Quadro P600 Mobile]
- Ubuntu 22.04.3 LTS

By modelling the measurements gathered in the FUB dataset with a graph, we obtain a network characterized by the attributes listed in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1

Graph properties	Cardinality
Nodes:	228,692
Edges:	14,438,078
Edges Frequency:	68,761,542
Virtualized DU:	2,670

Table 2

Operators	N° Graph Nodes
MNO_A	69,065
MNO_B	74,698
MNO_C	84,929

Table 3

Operators	Area	Cluster
A	MILANO	10
A	ROMA	9
B	MILANO	8
C	MILANO	7
C	ROMA	7
B	ROMA	7
A	NAPOLI	7
C	COLOGNO MONZESE	6
C	FRANCAVILLA AL MARE	6
C	GENOVA	5
C	MELITO DI NAPOLI	5
C	PALERMO	5

²The Fondazione Ugo Bordoni is an institution dedicated to higher education and research, under the supervision of the Ministry of Enterprises and Made in Italy.

Figure 4: Clustering of RUs for the top three MNOs using MDT data along the Rome motorway network (MN)

Subsequently, we employed the Leiden algorithm to cluster the RU nodes in the graph. The resulting clusters are illustrated in Figures 3³. Table 3 presents the clusters for the main Italian municipalities. Figure 4 provides a detailed view of the RU clustering results for the Rome area. The number of RUs partitions depends on the value of the resolution parameter γ . We used a value of $\gamma = 0.0001$ that creates clusters with many elements, but we used the constraint of not allocating more than 1008 elements within a cluster. In this way we have optimized the allocation of all RUs on all clusters taking into account the connections of RUs to UEs detected in the geographical area served by these clusters and the limit on the number of admissible RUs.

³Figures 3, 4, and 8 can only be understood if printed in color

Figure 5: Leiden algorithm exec. time vs. resolution parameter

The Leiden algorithm's results also depend on the number of iterations I . The configuration of these two parameters, γ and I , significantly influence the outcome, affecting both the number of detected clusters and the execution time of the Leiden algorithms. Using a very small resolution parameter will decrease the number of clusters, whereas increasing the number of iterations will yield more accurate results at the expense of longer execution time.

Figure 6: Leiden algorithm execution time vs. iterations

Figures 5 and 6 illustrate the impact of these input configuration parameters on the total execution time of the RU clustering algorithm. In particular, Figure 5 depicts the relationship between the resolution parameter and execution time, while Figure 6 correlates the number of iterations with execution time. Figure 7 illustrates the variation in the number of clusters detected by the algorithm across different resolution parameter settings. As the resolution parameter increases, the number of detected clusters also grows. Notably, the algorithm can automatically determine the number of iterations, with execution ceasing when no further improvements occur

between iterations. Furthermore, clustering reveals key RUs in the access network. RUs with a high betweenness centrality are involved in inter-DU handover procedures due to their position at the border between RAN network segments. Conversely, although involved in inter-DU HO procedures, the RUs with high betweenness centrality are those whose position minimises communication delays by improving network efficiency. RUs with high eigenvector centrality are well-connected to other influential RUs within the cluster, increasing their involvement in intra-DU handovers. Figure 8 illustrates the RUs with the highest betweenness, closeness, and eigenvector centrality values for RAN of MNO C in the Rome urban area, highlighted in green, yellow, and red, respectively. ref

5 Conclusions

We have shown how to exploit Leiden’s algorithm to cluster radio units (RUs) to facilitate intra-DU and inter-DU handovers for highly mobile users. Through meticulous analysis of the data collected from the minimisation driving tests (MDTs), the positioning of distributed units (DUs) and central units (CUs) concerning clusters of radio units (RUs) can be fine-tuned, resulting in a much more efficient handover process. This methodology may reduce the signalling load and latency, thus improving the quality of service for users. Improved performance, such as reliability and reduced service interruptions, underlines the importance of adopting policies at the RIC level that favour localised and less complex handover procedures. Adopting this clustering algorithm facilitates smoother and more efficient handover management and sets a new benchmark for mobile network optimisation, which is crucial to support latency-sensitive applications. These promising results encourage further exploration and development in network function virtualisation and advanced mobile traffic management, suggesting a strong potential for future technological advances in mobile communication infrastructures.

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(a) Geoposition of MDT data;

(b) RUs Clusters for Operator A

(c) RUs Clusters for Operator B

(d) RU Clusters for Operator C

Figure 3: Clustering of RU data from MDT data for DU/CU allocation for the top three italian MNOs

Figure 7: Number of clusters detected by Leiden algorithm versus resolution parameter

Figure 8: High betweenness, closeness and eigenvector centrality RUs for MNO C within Rome urban area